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The Self-Esteem, Loneliness, and Psychological Well-Being of Online Dating App Users: A Mixed Method Study

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Abstract

This research investigates how self-esteem and loneliness affect the psychological well-being of Online Dating App Users in Bagumbayan, Bocaue, Bulacan, Philippines. Using a sequential exploratory design integrating qualitative and quantitative approaches, the study explores the experiences, challenges, coping strategies, and psychological attributes of 15 participants in the qualitative phase. The subsequent quantitative phase involves 200 respondents assessed through the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, UCLA Loneliness Scale, and Psychological Well-being Scale. The findings reveal a complex landscape: Online Dating App Users exhibit moderate self-esteem and loneliness levels while displaying aboveaverage psychological well-being. Statistically, a moderate positive correlation exists between self-esteem and psychological well-being, alongside a low yet significant correlation between loneliness and psychological well-being. These insights underpin the formulation of the "Swipe Right, Swipe Left: The Realities of Online Dating Apps Program," which aims to empower users and foster emotionally healthy connections within digital dating platforms through workshops and seminars. This study provides crucial insights into the psychological dynamics of Online Dating App Users, offering implications for research and practical interventions promoting well-being in the digital dating sphere.

Keywords: *self-esteem, loneliness, psychological well-being, online dating app users*

Introduction

A wide spread of social media exposed people to discover applications that can be useful for their lives. People often use social media platforms to connect and communicate with others worldwide. Hence, websites for communication make up social media, and they help people from different backgrounds develop relationships, creating a well-founded social structure (Kapoor et al., 2017). One of the relevant platforms in social media nowadays is Online Dating Applications. Online dating apps aim to connect with someone interested in intimacy, casual talking, or finding friends (Orchard, 2019). Thus, Jalili (2019) revealed that 49% of adults use the application to find a romantic relationship. Also, some people use these dating sites to forget about their recent break-ups, find someone to talk to, look for a friend, and be curious about how the application software works (Jalili, 2019). Online dating apps have been consistent and established as the new norm (Murden et al., 2020). Although some individuals have had spectacular success with online dating and have created meaningful relationships, others have struggled, which has left them feeling disappointed and frustrated (Nicholson, 2014, as cited by, StudyMoose, 2019). The study by Toma (2022) showed that online dating app users' psychological well-being possessed psychosocial vulnerabilities such as anxiety, avoidance, attachment anxiety, and rejection sensitivity. It implies that negative psychological aspects often occur among online dating app users.

Meanwhile, levels of body shame and negative views regarding their body weight and shape increased with how frequently they checked online dating apps (Rodgers et al., 2019). It implies that men and women, in particular, could show higher levels of body dissatisfaction and poor perceptions due to their frequent use of dating apps. This finding has shown the negative effects of online dating apps on the self-esteem of individuals. Bell (2021) stated that online dating apps affect an individual's psychological well-being. Thus, online dating apps tend to ruin or lower a person's self-esteem due to rejection and lack of matches as predictors. To support this statement, Marateck's (2018) study stated that people who use online dating apps have lower self-esteem than those who don't. Self-esteem is essential to a human's physical and psychological well-being as it can improve performance in education, social presentation, and other aspects of human life (Jordan et al., 2017). The study of Singhal and Prakash (2021) has shown that self esteem significantly affects psychological well-being. This finding implies that self-esteem among online dating app users can affect their psychological well-being in various aspects.

However, Pereira et al. (2017) revealed that self-esteem does not significantly affect psychological well-being. It indicates that self-esteem does not predict the psychological well-being of online dating app users. Loneliness has been extensively researched as one of the psychological factors that eventually caused obsessive online media use and negative outcomes (Coduto et al., 2020). Thus, it signals that one's perceived social relationships (attachments) are not at the desired level, inspiring efforts to change one's situation and escape from the undesirable state (Cacioppo et al., 2006, as cited by Elder et al., 2017). According to Cacioppo et al. (2002, as cited by Mahdavifar, 2020), as loneliness elicits higher risks of developing negative psychological aspects such as depression, most individuals cope by striving to pursue romantic relationships using online dating apps. It was revealed that loneliness significantly correlates with psychological well-being (Ishaq et al., 2018). Thus, the result implies that loneliness can affect the psychological well-being of online dating app users. However, the study by Cahyadi (2019) has shown a very weak negative correlation between loneliness and psychological well-being. This finding indicates a lower effect of loneliness on the psychological well-being of online dating app users.

Furthermore, self-esteem and loneliness are crucial parts of the psychological aspects of an individual's mind. Similar studies have shown that social media platforms, such as online dating sites, can positively affect an individual's psychological well-being, and self-esteem and decrease feelings of loneliness (MahdaviFar, 2020). However, other studies claim that even though dating apps offer matchmaking services, they can be unpleasant for users as they become overly dependent on virtual validation. They may also feel pressured to adhere to specific social norms and endure peer pressure. Nevertheless, the stigma related to psychological conditions might be dangerous for their mental well-being, which is frequently disregarded (Bhatia, 2020). Moreover, this study investigates the effect of self-esteem and loneliness on the psychological well-being of online dating app users and how they affect one another. Thus, this study will also explore online dating app users' lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms. The study's findings will serve as a basis for developing the Online Dating Apps Awareness Program (ODAAP). This program will raise awareness among people regarding the psychological effects of online dating apps, which may also help psychology practitioners to discover possible interventions.

Research Questions

This study investigates the effect of self-esteem and loneliness on the psychological well-being of Online Dating App users. Specifically, to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of Online Dating App Users?
2. What are the challenges faced by Online Dating App Users?
3. What are the coping mechanisms of Online Dating App Users?
4. How may the respondents' self-esteem be described?
5. How may the respondents' loneliness be described?
6. How may the respondents' psychological well-being be described?
7. Does self-esteem significantly affect the psychological well-being of Online Dating App Users?
8. Does loneliness significantly affect the psychological well-being of Online Dating App Users?
9. Based on the results of the study, what program can be formulated?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed methods research approach known as the sequential exploratory design which is defined by Creswell (2018) as an approach that integrates both qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis in a series of distinct phases within a single study, aiming to obtain a comprehensive understanding of a research problem (Dawadi et al., 2021). Through this approach, qualitative and quantitative methods were strategically employed to determine the sequence of data collection and analysis, ensuring relevance in the gathered information (Ivankova et al., 2006, as cited in Saliya, 2023). Additionally, this design outlines specific stages where qualitative and quantitative data results are interconnected and synthesized to offer a more nuanced comprehension of the research problem.

The sequential exploratory design employed two distinct phases. In the initial phase, the study adopted Heideggerian "Hermeneutics" phenomenology as its qualitative research approach, attributed to Martin Heidegger. This methodology, as noted by Miles et al. (2013, cited in Blanco et al., 2023), was chosen for its capability to illuminate the intricate nature of lived experiences and delve into their deeper meanings. By employing a hermeneutic framework, researchers emphasized the significance of narratives portraying individuals' everyday interactions with the subject under investigation. These stories were further analyzed and rearranged to convey their significance to others. Thus, to create meaning and attain comprehension, it was essential to uncover specific details and seemingly unimportant elements of experiences that were often overlooked in people's day-to-day lives (Sloan & Bowe, 2014, as cited by Blanco, 2023).

In the second phase of this study, a quantitative research approach was used, employing research questionnaires for self-esteem, loneliness, and psychological well-being. In addition, a descriptive-causal approach was used to assess the data gathered using the quantitative method to identify the level of self-esteem, loneliness, and psychological well-being among online dating app users and if their self-esteem and loneliness can affect their psychological well-being (Jefferys, 2018).

Furthermore, the results of both qualitative and quantitative phases were integrated and analyzed together. Specifically, the qualitative results were used to gain a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences and perspectives. On the other hand, the quantitative results were used to provide a broader understanding of the relationships between variables. Moreover, the integrated results were interpreted with how the qualitative findings served as a guide for the formulation of specific research questions for the quantitative phase that followed and involved the use of questionnaires to collect quantitative data. Thus, this approach aimed to determine whether the results from a small sample of individuals in the qualitative phase could be generalized to a large sample in the quantitative phase (Creswell, 2018)

Respondents

The initial phase of the current study involved recruiting participants and administering the interview guide and research instruments.

The study was conducted in Bagumbayan, Bocaue, Bulacan, Philippines, to ensure a diverse sample. Fifteen participants were selected to participate in in-depth individual interviews as part of the qualitative phase. In the study's second phase, 200 respondents were recruited to complete 27 the research questionnaires as part of the quantitative phase. The summary of the participant's demographic characteristics involved in the qualitative phase study is shown in Table 1

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Participants*

<i>Participant code</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Relationship Status</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Online dating app/s</i>
1	23	Single	Male	Tinder and Bumble
2	20	Single	Female	Tinder, Bumble, & Azar
3	20	Single	Male	Tinder and Omegle
4	22	Single	Female	Tinder and Bumble
5	22	Single	Male	Tinder and Bumble
6	21	Single	Male	Tinder and Bumble
7	22	Single	Male	Tinder and Bumble
8	21	Single	Female	Skout
9	19	Single	Male	Tinder and Bumble
10	19	Single	Male	Tinder
11	22	In a relationship	Female	Omegle
12	20	Single	Female	Ometv and Omegle
13	23	In a relationship	Female	Tinder and Tantan
14	25	Single	Male	Tinder and Bumble
15	21	Single	Female	Tinder, Bumble, and Badoo

Instrument

A semi-structured interview was explicitly designed for Online Dating App users, following ethical research principles and obtaining informed consent from participants before conducting the quantitative and qualitative phases, specifically the in-depth interview in conducting the qualitative phase (UK Statistics Authority, 2022). The process of acquiring data included developing a rapport with the participants. Before joining, participants were informed about the study's nature, objectives, and significance. The researcher developed a semi-structured interview guide. This guide was reviewed and validated by licensed psychologists before interviews. The interview focused on (1) the experiences of online dating app users, (2) the challenges they encounter; and (3) coping mechanisms. Quantitative Research Instrument Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale instrument used in this study was developed by Morris Rosenberg in 1965. It consists of 10 statements assessing positive and negative feelings towards oneself, reflecting on general feelings of self-worth or self-acceptance. The reliability of this scale was high, with an internal consistency of 0.77 and a minimum coefficient of reproducibility of at least 0.90 (Kusuma & Yuliawati, 2020). This instrument's usage within this study aimed to evaluate and measure self-esteem levels within the study's selected population, Bagumbayan, Bocaue, Bulacan, providing valuable 30 insights into online dating app users' perceptions of self-worth. The scale is considered unidimensional as all items were answered on a 4-point Likert scale and the following rating scale was employed and rearranged:

<i>Rating Scale</i>	<i>Ranges</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	1-1.49	Low
2	1.5- 2.49	Average
3	2.5-3.49	High
4	3.5-4	Very High

UCLA Loneliness Scale

The UCLA Loneliness (Version 3) instrument was developed by Daniel Russell in 1996. It was composed of 20 items that were scored on a scale of 1 to 4, with 1 indicating "Never," 2 indicating "Rarely," 3 indicating "Sometimes," and 4 indicating "Often." The scoring for the nine items (1,5,6,9,10,15,16,19, and 20) was said to be reversed. Thus, high scores indicated higher loneliness levels with a Cronbach's alpha reliability of .89 to .94 (Safa & Majeed, 2020). In this study, the UCLA Loneliness scale was utilized to assess and quantify the levels of loneliness experienced by online dating app users within the study's targeted population, providing critical insights into the prevalence and intensity of loneliness among online dating app users in Bagumbayan, Bocaue, Bulacan.

Psychological Well-being Scale (PWBS)

The Psychological Well-being Scale (PWBS) instrument was developed by Carol Ryff in 1989 and was adapted by Ryff and Keyes in 1995. The 42-item Psychological Well-being Rating Scale Ranges Verbal Interpretation 1 1 – 1.49 Low 2 1.5 – 2.49 Average 3 2.5 – 3.49 High 4 3.5 - 4 Very High Rating Scale Ranges Verbal Interpretation 1 1-1.49 Low 2 1.5 - 2.49 Average 3 2.5 - 3.49 High 4 3.5 - 4 Very High 31 scale had six subscales: Self-acceptance, Environmental mastery, Positive relations with others, Autonomy, Personal growth, and Purpose in life. The questionnaire indicated one's degree of disagreement using a score ranging from 1-6 (strongly disagree to strongly agree). The scoring instructions were to reverse-score each negatively worded item (Celestine, 2021). The computed

Cronbach alpha for each subscale showed: Purpose in life (.70), autonomy (.72), Positive relations with others (.79), Personal growth (.76), Environmental mastery (.81), Self-acceptance (.85). Thus, the overall computed internal consistency for the PWBS scale ranged from .86 to .93 (Manchiraju, 2020). In the context of this study, the PWBS was employed to comprehensively measure the psychological wellbeing of online dating app users in Bagumbayan, Bocaue, Bulacan, allowing for a nuanced understanding of their well-being across multiple dimensions. The Likert scale rating has been modified as follows:

<i>Rating Scale</i>	<i>Ranges</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	1-1.49	Very Low
2	1.5- 2.49	Low
3	2.5-3.49	Average
4	3.5-4.49	Above Average
5	4.50-5.49	High
6	5.50-6.00	Very High

Data Analysis

In the qualitative phase of the study, Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) by Moustakas in 1994 was used to analyze qualitative data. The first step in the analysis involved transcribing the interviews into written documents. These documents were then analyzed to identify themes representing the participants' experiences. The analysis process involved reading the interviews several times to understand the results better. Thus, important quotes were highlighted and grouped into more significant themes. These themes were analyzed to find connections and relationships where the qualitative data was compared to quantitative data to see how well they matched up. As a result, it ensured that the qualitative data was reliable and accurate (Gil-Rodriguez, 2022). On the other hand, during the quantitative phase, the statistical techniques that were used included: 1. Analyzing the level and characteristics of the respondents' self-esteem, loneliness, and psychological well-being was done by utilizing descriptive statistics like mean. 2. Linear regression analysis was used to investigate the effect of self-esteem and loneliness on the psychological well-being of the respondents. This analysis allowed the researchers to determine the extent to which self-esteem and loneliness could predict psychological well-being among online dating app users.

Ethical Consideration

Protecting human subjects was of utmost importance in any research study, and ethical principles were strictly followed. This was especially crucial when conducting face-to-face and digital interviews, as in this study on "Online Dating App Users." Participants who met the criteria for involvement were provided with written informed consent, with the assistance of the researchers, before being included in the study. The ethical principles were emphasized at each stage of the research process, with the nature and goals of the study explained clearly to participants. They were assured that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time without any adverse consequences. Confidentiality was also ensured, with data collected in accordance with data protection regulations and kept only for academic and research purposes. In accordance with Republic Act No. 10173, protecting a person's private information was obligatory. In addition to written informed consent, researchers also obtained their consent for the audio recording of their interviews. The researchers also took into account the availability of participants and personally conducted the interviews, ensuring that no payment was required from the participants. Moreover, throughout the study, the researchers maintained a professional, respectful, and courteous demeanor to prevent any harm or distress to the participants.

Results and Discussion

Qualitative Phase

In this phase, the researchers explore the narratives and experiences of online dating app users, revealing three significant themes that emerge as the outcomes of the analysis: 'Self-Worth and Appraisal,' 'Seeking Connection in a Digital World,' and 'Balancing Well-Being and App Use'.

Table 1. *The Analysis*

<i>Subordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Self-worth and Appraisal Seeking	Impact of Negative Feedback Self-Presentation Strategies Validation through Positive Interactions
Seeking Connection in a Digital World	Digital Comfort of Loneliness Digital Frustrations
Balancing Well-being and App Use	Navigating Rejections and Disappointments Self-care Practices Awareness of Emotional Responses Setting Boundaries

Self-Worth and Appraisal

In the realm of online dating apps, users often find themselves on a dynamic journey of self-discovery and validation. In support, Kwok

and Wescott, (2020) stated that 35 in the digital age of romance, people constantly evaluate their self-worth through the lens of app interaction. Thus, this theme reflects these complex feelings, as users encounter the positive and negative aspects of their self-esteem. Within this theme, the researchers explore three interconnected subthemes: "Validation through Positive Interactions," "Self-Presentation Strategies," and the "Impact of Negative Feedback." These subthemes illuminate the complex relationship between self-esteem, personal presentation, and emotional responses in the context of online dating, providing invaluable insights into how individuals strive to project a desirable image, seek validation, and navigate the emotional conflict inherent in dating app-based connections.

Validation through Positive Interactions

In online dating apps, individuals often find their self-esteem and self-worth significantly influenced by the quality and quantity of meaningful interactions they encounter, reflecting the transformative potential of these online interactions (Alexopoulos et al., 2019). This subtheme underscores the profound impact that meaningful conversations and affirming encounters within the realm of online dating apps can have on an individual's self-esteem and confidence. When the participants were asked how can online dating apps affect their self-esteem, the majority of them answered that the app can affect them positively as it boosts their confidence. Specifically, Participant 1 stated that the more he talks to a lot of people on online dating apps, the more it boosts his confidence, allowing him to feel like he can talk to anyone.

Nabboost niya [ng online dating apps] yung self-esteem ko. Parang nagiging confident ako [...] kapag lalong dumadami yung nakakausap ko, feel ko nagiging confident ako. Kaya kong kausapin yung kahit sino. (My self-esteem has been boosted [by online dating apps]. I feel like I'm becoming confident [...] when I talk to more and more people, I feel like I'm becoming confident. It's like, I can talk to anyone.)

The participants express how their self-esteem experiences a significant boost through their engagement with an increasing number of people. According to our data, 47% of the participant population acknowledged experiencing a boost in self-esteem through positive interactions on online dating apps, supporting sentiments similar to those expressed by Participant 1. This suggests that positive interactions on the dating app serve as a source of validation, fostering a sense of self-worth and self-assurance. Thus, such validation appears to empower the individual, enabling them to approach conversations with a newfound confidence. This supports Malz's (2020) claim that interactions on dating apps can serve as a means of validation, supporting people's feelings of their desirability and self-worth.

Further, aside from gaining confidence from talking to a lot of people on online dating apps, Participant 3 stated that he finds online dating apps helpful for handling his insecurities. According to him, people in online dating apps often encourage him whenever he opens up about his insecurities.

At some point, nakakaapekto yung dating app sa self-esteem ko kasi yung mga nakakausap ko don madalas ko silang sabihan regarding sa insecurities ko ganon, tapos ayon, may sinasabi sila na ano, parang nakakaencourage sakin na ayos lang na ganon, kaya ayon, nabboost yung self-esteem ko. (At some point, the dating app affects my self-esteem because I talk to people there regarding my insecurities, they say something that seems to encourage me that it's okay, so yeah, my self-esteem was boosted.)

Participant 3's perspective further emphasizes the transformative potential of these online interactions. It was revealed that online dating app occasionally affects the users' self-esteem, primarily due to conversations where they discuss their insecurities. Nevertheless, these interactions take a positive direction as others give encouraging words, informing them that having certain flaws is normal. This type of encouragement and 37 support found in the online dating realm becomes a form of validation, helping to the improvement of their self-esteem.

Moreover, the statements of the participants were aligned with the claim made by Finkel et al. (2012, as cited by, Antheunis et al., 2020), highlighting that online dating app interactions can indeed serve as a means of validation, reinforcing individuals' perceptions of their desirability and self-worth. Through these exchanges, individuals find not only potential romantic connections but also a valuable boost to their self-esteem, enabling them to navigate the digital dating landscape with greater confidence and positivity.

Self-Presentation Strategies

Individuals engage in a developing experience as they redefine how they portray themselves to potential partners, going beyond fundamental physical appearance. This development involves shifting from self-doubt and fear to newfound self-confidence and self-acceptance (Waters, 2021). Users learn to appreciate their unique attributes and embrace a more authentic presentation of themselves in the online dating setting. This process of self-discovery and empowerment corresponds with more extensive research on online dating, which suggests that these platforms give individuals an opportunity to experiment with self-presentation, supporting increased self-esteem and personal growth (Vaingankar et al., 2022).

This subtheme underscores the developing nature of online dating apps in reshaping individuals' self-perception and confidence in presenting themselves. Prior to using dating apps, Participant 6 shared that he struggled with shyness and a lack of self-confidence, particularly in terms of his physical appearance. He characterizes himself negatively. However, as he navigated the online dating app platforms, he gradually began to embrace the idea that how he presents himself goes beyond physical appearance. This reflects a shift

from external validation to internal self-assurance.

Before, I used to be very shy, na hindi ako ganun ka confident to face people na kasi like before parang I was seeing myself na parang negative na yung physical appearance ko, so, parang isa na rin sa challenge sa dating app yung how you present yourself physically but through sa dating app parang unti-unti ko siyang na-embrace na it's how you present yourself and kung ano man ang sabihin ng iba okay lang, na kung ayaw nila sayo, okay lang din. Siguro, mas naging confident akong i-present yung sarili ko and mas natutunan ko na hindi i-value masyado and hindi pakinggan yung opinion ng ibang tao. (Before, I used to be very shy, that I wasn't that confident to face people because like before I was seeing myself as if my physical appearance was negative, so, it seems like one of the challenges in the dating app is how you present yourself physically but also, through the dating app, I seem to have gradually embraced that it's how you present yourself and whatever others' opinion is okay, that if they don't like you, that's okay too. Maybe, I became more confident to present myself and I learned more not to value too much and not to listen to other people's opinions.)

Participant 6's experience emphasizes the power of online dating apps in encouraging aging individuals to present themselves authentically and with greater self-confidence. According to the data, 53% of the participant population shared comparable experiences, emphasizing the transformative journey of self-discovery and enhanced self-confidence in online self-presentation, aligning with the subtheme highlighted in the qualitative findings. It implies that the digital realm allows users to experiment with self-presentation in a way that can foster newfound self-assuredness. In support of the findings, Tong et al. (2020), stated that online dating environments often enable individuals to craft and refine their self-image, contributing to enhanced self-esteem and self-presentation skills.

Additionally, Participant 1's perspective provides additional context. He notes that the dating app has encouraged him to "be more open about who he is" and to show people who you really are. This highlights the role of dating apps in promoting self-acceptance and a focus on individuality rather than conforming to external standards.

Thus, this subtheme reveals how online dating apps can serve as platforms for personal growth and self-acceptance. It provides a space where individuals learn to value themselves beyond physical appearance, fostering self-confidence and an embrace of their uniqueness in the process.

Impact of Negative Feedback

The emotional impact of negative experiences, such as ghosting and rejection, hold a significant place in the realm of online dating apps, as evidenced by the experiences of users within this digital platform (Anderson et al. 2020). Ghosting involves the sudden and unexplained end of communication by an individual in an online conversation. It often leaves the other person feeling confused, hurt, and emotionally vulnerable. Rejection, on the other hand, occurs when an individual explicitly expresses disinterest or declines to pursue a romantic connection. This can be also emotionally challenging, as it involves the explicit dismissal of one's romantic advances (Gould, 2022).

These experiences are not uncommon within online dating platforms and often create emotional challenges, as individuals invest their emotions, expectations, and often a sense of vulnerability in these interactions. In this study, most of the participants struggle with these kinds of situations. Participant 14 recounts a deeply emotional encounter of being ghosted for the first time, an experience marked by the initial formation of a strong connection with a person he met on an online dating app. However, the sudden break of communication and later discovering about the other person's new relationship on social media caused profound pain and emotional distress.

Yung una, na-ghost ako. First time ko yun. [...] Siya yung malala kasi, pinaparamdam niya sa'kin na special ako. Parang nag assume din talaga ako na may mapupuntahan yung pag-uusap namin. Tapos, one day, biglang di nagchachat. Tapos edi inistalk ko yung fb niya, nakita ko may boyfriend na. Sobrang na-hurt ako dun. Umabot ako sa point na umiyak ako no'n. [...] Tapos ayun, yun yung isa sa experience ko sa ghost ako— pagkakaghost sa'kin. Meron naman, ni-reject ako. Ano... manliligaw na ako dapat pero ayaw niya. Tapos simula no'n, hindi na kami nag-usap. Wala na. (The first one, I was ghosted. It was my first time. [...] It was a bad one because she makes me feel special. It's like I really assumed that our conversation would lead to something. Then, one day, suddenly we stopped chatting. Then I stalked her fb, I saw that she already has a boyfriend. I was very hurt by that. I reached the point where I cried. [...] Then, that was one of my experiences with my ghost – being ghosted. Yes, I was rejected. I'm supposed to be a lover but she doesn't want to. Then from then on, we didn't talk anymore. Gone.)

This interaction highlights the vulnerability that individuals can experience while seeking connection on dating apps and the substantial impact that negative interactions can have on their psychological well-being. This feeling is also expressed by Participant 1's perspective, who recalls experiencing rejection in a similar manner. In our findings, 53% of the participant population shared similar experiences, highlighting the emotional toll of negative experiences, such as ghosting and rejection, within the realm of online dating apps. Their initial hopes of forming a romantic relationship ended when the other person showed no interest in them. Thus, the rejection led to a complete break of communication, causing feelings of disappointment and potentially even lower self-esteem.

These situations highlight the emotional vulnerabilities that are present in the world of online dating, where participants bring feelings and expectations to this online interaction. In support of this finding, de Wiele and Campbell (2019), revealed that negative feedback in online dating platforms, such as ghosting and rejection, can be particularly distressing due to the emotional investment individuals put into these connections. The emotional responses shown here highlight the importance of understanding how individuals must

carefully balance their search for meaningful connections with the need to protect their own emotional well-being when faced with potential disappointments in the world of online dating.

Seeking Connection in a Digital World

In the context of the digital world, an individual could meet a lot of people to seek genuine connections and personal relationships. According to Asamoah (2018), individuals are living in a time of greater digital connectivity. The majority of people have hundreds or even thousands of friends, connections, and contacts on social media sites, however, there is a constant increase in reports of loneliness (Asamoah, 2018). Thus, this theme provides insight into how users' attitudes toward online dating apps are exposed and how these influence their emotions of loneliness and dissatisfaction.

There are two related subthemes under this theme, such as "Digital Comfort of Loneliness" and "Digital Frustrations". These two subthemes show what triggers users to use online dating apps on the internet as well as how these apps impact their feelings of loneliness and frustration.

Digital Comfort of Loneliness

Online dating makes it easier for individuals to connect with a wide variety of people while minimizing the uncertainty that comes with face-to-face interactions as it focuses on the idea that everyone is single and looking for a connection (Seidman, 2019). Individuals who are lonely might also use internet interactions to make up for a lack of offline social connections. However, this ease of engagement may also raise concerns about potential misuse, particularly among lonely individuals (Seidman, 2019).

This subtheme underscores the influence of the digital realm on the factors that drive users to utilize dating apps. It emphasizes that users turn to online dating applications due to various reasons such as boredom, loneliness, and other factors. When questioned about his motivation for using online dating apps, Participant 6 cited his lack of social connections, particularly during pandemics, as a driving factor. Additionally, he mentioned that people turn to these apps because they experience feelings of isolation and loneliness.

Noong pandemic, there's no chance to meet so, nag trigger din sakin na [gumamit ng online dating app dahil] minsan I feel lonely and maybe alone ka na gusto mong makakilala ng tao na hindi mo pa kilala aside your friends, your family, peers, or yung mga people na nakapaligid sayo. So, parang mag gusto mong magreach ng other person. (During the pandemic, there's no chance to meet so, it also triggered me to [use an online dating app because] sometimes I feel lonely and maybe you're alone that you want to meet someone you don't know yet aside from your friends, your family, peers, or the people around you. So, you seem to want to reach for other people.)

Participant 6's statement highlights the variety of motivations that drive individuals to use online dating apps. He attributed his decision to use online dating apps to the pandemic, which limited opportunities for physical social interaction. In our data, a substantial 80% of the participant population expressed a shared sentiment, emphasizing the digital comfort provided by online dating in addressing feelings of loneliness. This situation triggered a sense of loneliness and a desire to connect with new people outside their existing social circles. Thus, this illustrates the role of online dating apps as a remedy for loneliness and a means to expand one's social connections.

Similarly, Participant 2 stated that aspects such as being bored and lonely at the same time led her to use online dating services. She also mentioned that she had chosen to use dating apps at the time because she was seeking the attention and love she desired.

Nag-udyok sa akin na gumamit ng online dating app kasi bored ako. Lonely na rin. Parang that time naghahanap ka ng love na gusto mong maramdaman. Naghahanap ka ng atensyon na gusto mong maranasan— gusto kong maranasan. So that's why nagdownload ako ng mga dating app para mafulfill yung mga gusto kong maramdaman. (I was triggered to use an online dating app because I was bored. Lonely too. It's like at that time you are looking for the love you want to feel. You are looking the attention you want to experience— I want to experience. So that's why I download dating apps to fulfill what I want to feel.)

Participant 2 emphasizes the role of boredom and loneliness as motivating factors for using dating apps. The desire to experience love and attention led her to download online dating apps. This reflects the broader theme that digital dating environments provide individuals with a platform to seek connection and fulfillment, particularly when faced with feelings of loneliness or a need for attention. Supporting this view, Blaire (2019) asserts that although the initial emphasis of online dating was on finding romantic partners, there is a growing concern that the advent of smartphone dating applications, which allow users to connect based on proximity, has shifted the focus toward less serious sexual relationships. This shift can be partly attributed to the fact that some individuals turn to online dating apps out of feelings of loneliness and a desire for more immediate connections, potentially leading to a focus on short-term and less serious interactions.

Digital Frustration

One of the most common frustrations faced by online dating app users is the sheer number of options available on dating apps. The lack of openness when it comes to people's intentions is another issue with dating apps. Some users seek committed relationships, while others contend with casual encounters or even just an ego boost (Lyons, 2023). This sub-theme focuses on the impact on users who do not find a suitable match despite their interactions on dating apps, resulting in frustration. When the participants were asked about the challenges they face in online dating apps, one participant mentioned experiencing frustration, especially when they engage with someone on dating apps who appears to be serious but no mutual match occurs. Participant 5, for instance, mentioned that the

individuals he chatted with had acceptable appearances, but their compatibility did not align with his expectations.

Pag nag swipe right ako kasi good looking yung tao, tapos hindi siya nagmatch, so parang nafufrustrate ako kasi based sa looks niya type ko siya so nafufrustrate ako pag hindi nagmamatch ganon. (For me, when I swipe right because the person is goodlooking, then he doesn't match, so I feel frustrated because, based on his looks, he is my type, so I get frustrated when he doesn't match, something like that.)

Participant 5's statement provides a clear illustration of the frustration that can arise within online dating platforms. This participant describes their frustration when swiping right on someone they find visually appealing, only to discover that there is no mutual match. In our findings, 53% of the participant population expressed a shared frustration, highlighting the challenges faced by users of online dating apps. The source of their frustration lies in the misalignment between the individual's physical appearance and their expectations, highlighting the significance of attraction and visual preferences in the online dating experience.

This subtheme emphasizes how users frequently experience irritation when their expectations—which are frequently shaped by indications of appearance and individual preferences—do not match the results of their interactions on dating apps. Given the emotional complexities present in these digital interactions, it is essential to investigate how people manage and process these feelings in order to gain a deeper knowledge of the online dating experience.

This emotional response aligns with findings from Castro and Barrada (2020), who highlighted those emotional reactions, including frustration, are common outcomes when users' expectations based on visual cues do not correspond with the results of their interactions on online dating apps. It underscores the need to explore how individuals navigate and cope with such emotions within the digital dating platform, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the online dating experience.

Balancing Well-Being and App Use

In today's digital age, the utilization of dating apps has seamlessly integrated into the daily lives of many individuals. According to Zorita et al. (2023), continuous access to these apps might have both positive and negative effects on an individual's well-being. While dating apps offer a convenient avenue to connect with potential partners, they also hold the potential to influence users' mental health. Users who wish to successfully navigate this complex environment must become competent at identifying and understanding their emotional reactions in order to decide what constitutes a state of balanced well-being in the context of their app usage. This theme intends to explore four interconnected subthemes: "Setting Boundaries," "Navigating Rejections and Disappointments," "SelfCare Practices," and "Awareness of Emotional Responses."

Setting Boundaries

Individuals are exposed to emotional vulnerability when engaging with new people, even in online interactions where they may initially feel secure. While dating apps provide convenience and prospects for interactions, they may have an adverse effect on someone's emotional state (Clarke, 2023). However, online dating apps empower users with a significant degree of control over the level of engagement they want to put into their matches and the dynamics of their relationships by implementing limitations and expectations on their profiles to guarantee their emotional safety (Zhou, 2023).

This subtheme highlights users' experiences and coping strategies in the context of online dating apps, emphasizing the significance of having clear boundaries and self-imposed limitations. In addition, Participant 3 shared how he doesn't allow himself to invest in emotions that he knows are harmful to him, particularly in online settings. This reflects the development of a sense of self-worth and personal improvement.

Hindi ko masyadong inallow yung sarili ko mag invest ng emotions na alam kong harmful para sa akin. Kumbaga dapat may boundaries pa rin kasi mahirap mag invest sa mga taong sa online mo lang nakilala. Kailangan talaga alam mo yung limitations mo. (I don't allow myself to invest emotions that I know are harmful for me. I guess there should still be boundaries because it's hard to invest in people you only met online. You really need to know your limitations.)

The statement of Participant 3 aligns with Chaturvedi (2023) claim that when it comes to online dating, individuals prioritize the establishment of boundaries to guarantee their emotional safety and avoid heartbreak when meeting new people. In our data, 53% of the participant population stated a shared sentiment, underscoring the importance of setting boundaries and implementing limitations within the realm of online dating apps. They express their limitations and boundaries as soon as they match with someone. This implies that users are exposed to a wide range of individuals, increasing their chances of finding what they're looking for while also taking a cautious approach by prohibiting themselves from engaging in emotions that could cause harm to themselves. This emphasizes the importance of self-awareness and establishing boundaries when it comes to online dating.

Navigating rejections and disappointments

In an online dating app, rejections and disappointments are common since they are a normal part of the dating experience. This prevalence is partly due to the huge number of potential matches available in the dating pool, which increases the likelihood that one's interest won't always be reciprocated (Collisson, 2022). Nevertheless, as users navigate their way through these digital dating apps, rejections will occur frequently. However, these experiences may also be an important component in shaping the kind of relationships

that genuinely bring happiness, representing a shift from rejection to opportunity and hope.

This subtheme underscores how rejections and disappointments are present in online dating contexts and sheds light on how users transform them into opportunities or reasons to discover more compatible individuals rather than being unhappy with how their matches turn out. Notably, participant 6 provides his viewpoint. He highlighted his capacity to view rejection as a source of hope and to value oneself more despite the fact that others do not feel the same way about him.

Natutunan ko yung pagbibigay ng value sa sarili ko kesa sa ibang tao. Tinitignan ko yung rejection as a hope kasi kaya ka niya nireject kasi may hindi siya nagustuhan, and minsan nawawalan na rin ako ng pake. Genuine ka naman pero sila hindi, pero ayun mas nahahandle ko naman siya ng maayos. Rejection can make or break you, ganun. (I learned to value myself more than other people. I see rejection as a hope because people might have rejected you because they didn't like something, and sometimes I just don't care. You happened to be genuine to them but they don't reciprocate, either way, I can handle the situation better. Rejection can make or break you, just like that.)

Moreover, participant 6 statement aligns with Campbell (2019) claim that despite the idea and experiences of rejection that online dating apps can bring, users often express being unaffected or unconcerned by it, as they will still use the app since it has a broader pool of potential partners and they may ultimately match with someone new. In our findings, a substantial 60% of the participant population expressed a shared perspective, emphasizing the prevalence of rejections and disappointments in the online dating 48 platforms. This subtheme highlights users' resilience and adaptive mindset as they navigate through these experiences, transforming rejections into opportunities for discovering more compatible connections and fostering self-value.

Thus, individuals also hold the perspective that rejection in the online setting is perceived as less emotionally painful than it is in person. This explains why users tend to be more resilient in the face of disappointment and rejection in the context of online dating.

Self-care Practices

To maintain one's physical and mental health, a person must be aware of it and use self-care mental health behaviors to deal with issues that arise in daily life. Enough selfcare mental health behaviors will boost a person's self-esteem and enable them to handle stress and anxiety or other related mental health issues (Auttama et al. 2021). Thus, a person with a strong sense of confidence will be better able to handle challenges in life and things such as self-care practices increase enjoyment and learning effectiveness while also promoting physical and mental health (Auttama et al., 2021).

This section highlights the vital importance of self-care for maintaining one's physical and mental well-being, particularly in the context of using online dating apps. Participant 15 says that there are many things that need to be considered if a person ever feels frustrated while using an online dating app as there are numerous people using applications like this and self-care is crucial in this type of circumstances.

Whenever I feel frustrated while using online dating app. I always think lang na ang dami pang taong gumagamit ng online dating app and dami pang tao na pwedeng possible matches ko. So, I think that's the best self-care. Na hindi mo dadamdamin yung frustration or rejection na mae-encounter mo while using an online dating app. (Whenever I feel frustrated while using online dating apps. I always think that there are so many more people who use online dating apps and many more people who can be my 49 possible matches. So, I think that's the best self-care. That you shouldn't be bothered about the frustration or rejection that you will encounter while using an online dating app.)

This subtheme emphasizes the profound significance of self-care as an essential coping mechanism, especially when navigating the complexities of online dating apps. As Participant 15 stated, it is crucial to consider self-care when dealing with frustrations in this context. In our data, a significant 60% of the participant population emphasized the importance of self-care practices for maintaining physical and mental well-being, particularly in the context of using online dating apps. This section underscores how individuals, like Participant 15, recognize the necessity of self-care in dealing with frustrations and challenges that may arise during their online dating experiences. Further, the number of individuals using these apps signifies that many potential matches exist, making it most important for users to practice self-care to effectively manage frustration and rejection encountered while engaging with online dating apps.

Participant 15's statement aligns with the findings of Ong et al. (2021), highlighting the importance of self-awareness and the ability to make informed decisions in the context of online dating app usage. Self-care, in this context, is not just about managing emotions but also about processing information and making rational decisions for one's own wellbeing.

Awareness of Emotional Responses

The capacity to conceive and convey one's own feelings as well as those of others is known as emotional awareness. There is proof that emotional intelligence improves the capacity to control one's emotions, relationships, and social complexity, as well as one's physical and mental health. Emotional awareness can make one's life easier to make connections, make relationships, and handle it properly (Lane, 2021).

Participating in online dating provides an invaluable opportunity to encounter a diverse array of individuals. As expressed by a participant, it fosters an increased awareness of the various personalities and behaviors of others. This newfound awareness can extend

beyond one's own experiences and contribute to a broader understanding of personal interactions. For instance, Participant 14 mentions a friend experiencing depression and the profound impact of being a supportive presence, even without firsthand experience of depression. This emphasizes how individuals can gain insights and improve their ability to handle diverse situations, particularly those related to mental health.

Maganda ring experience kasi marami akong nakikitang iba't ibang klase ng tao [at] mas nagiging aware ako sa ugali ng iba't ibang tao. Katulad sa kaibigan ko, may depression, atleast nakakatulong ako kahit konti sa kanya. Kumbaga atleast nandiyan pa rin ako, nagegets ko yung experience niya kahit hindi ko naexperience [yung] depression. Kumbaga base lang dun sa mga nakakausap ko parang may natutunan din ako kung paano ko ihandle yung mga bagay bagay. More on sa mental health lang din talaga. (It's also a good experience because I get to see many different types of people [and] I become more aware of different people's behavior. Just like my friend, who has depression, at least I can help him a little. I guess at least I'm still there, I got his experience even though I didn't experience [the] depression. It seems that just based on the people I talked to, I also learned something about how to handle things. More on mental health.)

Participant 14 serves as an example of this increased knowledge by admitting how online dating has helped them have a more comprehensive understanding of how individuals behave. They give a moving example of helping a friend who is depressed, illuminating the need for emotional intelligence. Despite the fact that they may not have directly experienced depression, the knowledge they have received from their contacts has enabled them to empathize and offer helpful support, highlighting the importance of online dating in developing a more informed and sympathetic individual.

Among the participants, a substantial 60% expressed the significance of emotional awareness, acknowledging its positive impact on navigating diverse interactions, relationships, and mental health, particularly in the context of online dating. This section emphasizes participants' shared experience in fostering a heightened awareness of emotions, as illustrated by Participant 14's reflection on supporting a friend experiencing depression.

Additionally, Participant 6 reinforces the significance of emotional awareness in online dating. He emphasizes the importance of presenting oneself honestly and transparently from the beginning of interactions. This transparency not only allows individuals to be authentic in their approach but also enables their potential partners to understand their preferences and boundaries.

Ako masasabi ko na from the start na kung ano yung gusto at ayaw ko. You have to present yourself in an honest and good way para-aware din siya kung paano ka niya iaapproach. And huwag masyadong mabilis maattach, so dapat i-work out na rin para rin sa iyong sanity. Ayusin yung attachment issues para mas madaling makapag move on sa maling tao. (Even from the start, I believe that I'm aware of what I like and dislike. You have to present yourself in an honest and good way so that the other person is also aware of how he will approach you. And don't get attached too quickly so you should work out for your sanity as well. Fix attachment issues to make it easier to move on with the wrong person.)

Participant 6 advises against forming attachments too quickly, highlighting the importance of self-preservation and emotional well-being. By addressing attachment issues, individuals can enhance their ability to move on from unsuitable connections, promoting healthier and more sustainable online dating experiences. Thus, it allows individuals to present themselves honestly and proactively in the online dating context, fostering a conducive environment for open and honest interactions. This aligns with the concept of setting boundaries and ensuring that individuals are empowered to communicate their emotional needs effectively, as highlighted by Smith (2021).

Quantitative Phase

In this phase, the focus shifts to numerical data and empirical measurements, with the goal of quantifying the effect of self-esteem and loneliness on the psychological well-being of online dating app users.

The Level of Self-Esteem of Online Dating App Users

Table 2 presents the mean value of self-esteem levels among online dating app users assessed using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale. A low interpretation of indicator 1 was shown, with a mean score of 1.91, falling within the range of "Average," which suggests that individuals possess an average self-perception. However, it could also be challenging to maintain a good view of oneself in some instances. In addition, Indicator 8, which is categorized as "High" and has the highest mean score of 2.87, indicates individuals express Indicators Mean Verbal Interpretation 1. I feel that I am a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others. 1.91 Average 2. I feel that I have a number of good qualities. 1.94 Average 3. All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure. 2.12 Average 4. I am able to do things as well as most people. 2.13 Average 5. I feel I do not have much to be proud of. 2.07 Average 6. I take a positive attitude toward myself. 2.01 Average 7. On the whole, I am satisfied with myself. 2.24 Average 8. I wish I could have more respect for myself. 2.87 High 9. I certainly feel useless at times. 2.67 High 10. At times I think that I am no good at all. 2.52 High Grand Total Mean: 2.25 Average 54 a desire for higher self-respect. Moreover, a grand total mean score of 2.25, indicative of "Average" on the scale, suggests that, on average, online dating app users tend to express positive self-esteem. This finding implies that a majority of individuals within this group demonstrate a degree of agreement with statements that reflect positive self-perceptions. These statements encompass aspects related to self-worth, self-acceptance, and a general sense of self-esteem. Thus, this agreement signifies that, within the context of online dating app usage, users exhibit mainly positive views of themselves, potentially influenced by the dynamics and interactions

that unfold within the online dating environment.

Table 2. *The Level of Self-Esteem*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I feel that I am a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.	1.91	Average
2. I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	1.94	Average
3. All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure.	2.12	Average
4. I am able to do things as well as most people.	2.13	Average
5. I feel I do not have much to be proud of.	2.07	Average
6. I take a positive attitude toward myself.	2.01	Average
7. On the whole, I am satisfied with myself.	2.24	Average
8. I wish I could have more respect for myself.	2.87	High
9. I certainly feel useless at times.	2.67	High
10. At times I think that I am no good at all.	2.52	High
Grand Total Mean:	2.25	Average

Legend – 1-1.49: Low, 1.5-2.49: Average, 2.5-3.49: High, 3.5-4: Very High

This finding supported the study of Bonilla-Zorita et al. (2021) on self-esteem enhancement among online dating app users and found that these individuals often experience increased self-esteem due to enhanced social interactions and opportunities for positive self-presentation on these platforms. This aligns with the study's result that on average, online dating app users typically exhibit positive self-esteem. In contrast, Strubel and Petrie (2017, as cited by Bonilla-Zorita et al. 2023), revealed that online dating app usage has negative effects, resulting in lower levels of self-esteem and body satisfaction.

The Level of Loneliness of Online Dating App Users

Table 3. *The Level of Loneliness of Online Dating App Users*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. How often do you feel that you are "in tune" with the people around you?	2.20	Average
2. How often do you feel that you lack companionship?	2.46	Average
3. How often do you feel that there's no one you can turn to?	2.44	Average
4. How often do you feel alone?	2.64	High
5. How often do you feel part of a group of friends?	2.03	Average
6. How often do you feel that you have a lot in common with people around you?	2.32	Average
7. How often do you feel that you are no longer close to anyone?	2.42	Average
8. How often do you feel that your interests and ideas are not shared by those around you?	2.50	High
9. How often do you feel outgoing and friendly?	2.26	Average
10. How often do you feel close to people?	2.13	Average
11. How often do you feel left out?	2.45	Average
12. How often do you feel that your relationships with others are not meaningful?	2.37	Average
13. How often do you feel that no one really knows you well?	2.79	High
14. How often do you feel isolated from others?	2.54	High
15. How often do you feel that you can find companionship when you want it?	2.32	Average
16. How often do you feel that there are people who really understand you?	2.29	Average
17. How often do you feel shy?	2.98	High
18. How often do you feel that people are around you but not with you?	2.71	High
19. How often do you feel that there are people you can talk to?	2.24	Average
20. How often do you feel that there are people you can turn to?	2.26	Average
Grand Total Mean:	2.42	Average

Legend – 1-1.49: Low, 1.5-2.49: Average, 2.5-3.49: High, 3.5-4: Very High

Table 3 below presents the mean value of loneliness levels among online dating app users, as measured by the UCLA Loneliness Scale. The lowest score was obtained in Indicator 5, with a mean score of 2.03, falling within the "Average" range on the scale. This suggests that individuals felt distant from others in some instances or exhibited a poor sense of belonging. On the other hand, indicator 17, which had the highest score of 2.98 and was classified as "High" in the table, was also presented. This suggests that individuals showed a high level of shyness, which may have presented difficulties in social settings. A total mean score of 2.42 was obtained, which corresponds to "Average" on the scale, indicating that, on average, individuals using online dating apps tend to exhibit a mild level of loneliness. This finding suggests that a significant proportion of

users report only a slight level of loneliness. The result could indicate the possible social advantages of using online dating apps, as they encourage an average amount of social connection, potentially reducing users' feelings of loneliness

A grand total mean score of 2.42 was obtained, which corresponds to "Average" on the scale, indicating that, on average, individuals using online dating apps tend to exhibit a mild level of loneliness. This finding suggests that a significant proportion of users report only a slight level of loneliness. The result could indicate the possible social advantages of using online dating apps, as they encourage an average amount of social connection, potentially reducing users' feelings of loneliness. To reinforce this interpretation, Castro and Barrada (2022) underscore the positive impact of online dating app usage in reducing loneliness.

The study highlighted how these platforms effectively enhance social connections, particularly for individuals with limited opportunities for face-to-face interactions. Further emphasizing that online dating app users generally report a mild level of loneliness, highlighting the potential benefits of these platforms in addressing social isolation and enhancing feelings of connectedness. In contrast, a study by Nikiforova (2020) found that online dating app users exhibited no significant reduction in loneliness compared to non-users.

The Level of Psychological Well-Being of Online Dating App Users

The Level of Psychological Well-Being Table 4.1 below presents the first domain of Carol Ryff's Psychological Well-Being, focusing on Autonomy. Autonomy refers to the ability to independently decide and make one's own decisions, without the need to seek approval from others and the ability to resist external influences (Sanchez, 2022). This aligns with the obtained grand total mean score of 3.95, falling into the 'Above Average' category, implying that individuals tend to value and demonstrate autonomy in several areas of their lives. Notably, this domain also got the highest mean score among the other domains, highlighting the significance of autonomy for individuals' overall psychological well-being.

Table 4.1. *The Level of Psychological Well-Being of Online Dating App User*

Autonomy			
Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	
1. I am not afraid to voice my opinions even when it contradicts that of most people.	4.16	Above Average	
7. My decisions are usually not influenced by other people's thought.	4.08	Above Average	
13. I tend to worry about what other people think of me.	3.84	Above Average	
19. I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions.	3.68	Above Average	
25. I have confidence in my opinions, even if they are contrary to the general consensus.	4.14	Above Average	
31. It is difficult for me to voice my own opinion on controversial matters.	3.58	Above Average	
37. I judge myself by what I consider important, not by the values that other people consider relevant.	4.19	Above Average	
Grand Total Mean:	3.95	Above Average	

Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High

These findings align with De-Juanas et al. (2020) study, which revealed that those individuals possessing more defined goals, exert more control over their environment, and the capacity to make better decisions for themselves tend to exhibit high levels of autonomy. The study underscores that the greater the perceived autonomy, the greater the level of wellbeing. In the context of online dating, having autonomy is crucial for fostering genuine connections, enabling users to independently choose their potential matches, engage on their own terms by setting boundaries. Thus, it contributes to a positive online dating experience aligned with their personal interests and values. This implies a significant correlation between autonomy and psychological well-being of online dating app users.

On the other hand, table 4.2 below presents a grand total mean score of 3.78 obtained in the environmental mastery domain, reflecting an individual's ability to take Autonomy Indicators Mean Verbal Interpretation 1. I am not afraid to voice my opinions even when it contradicts that of most people. 4.16 Above Average 7. My decisions are usually not influenced by other people's thought. 4.08 Above Average 13. I tend to worry about what other people think of me. 3.84 Above Average 19. I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions. 3.68 Above Average 25. I have confidence in my opinions, even if they are contrary to the general consensus. 4.14 Above Average 31. It is difficult for me to voice my own opinion on controversial matters. 3.58 Above Average 37. I judge myself by what I consider important, not by the values that other people consider relevant. 4.19 Above Average Grand Total Mean: 3.95 Above Average 58 Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High advantage of opportunities and adjust to the environment, demonstrating their capability to effectively manage various life circumstances (Celestine, 2021).

Table 4.2. *Environmental Mastery Domain*

Environmental Mastery		
Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
2. In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live.	4.09	Above Average
8. The daily demands often make me feel discouraged.	3.52	Above Average
14. I do not feel like I fit in with the people and community around me.	3.47	Average
20. I am quite able to manage my daily responsibilities.	4.24	Above Average
26. I often feel overburdened by my responsibilities	3.93	Above Average
32. I have trouble managing my life in a way	3.64	Above Average
38. I have been able to build my house and live according to what I like.	3.58	Above Average
Grand Total Mean:	3.78	Above Average

Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High

Even though certain areas could use improvement and growth, such as indicators 26 and 32, The overall mean score still stands in the ‘Above Average’ category. This implies an agreeable level of environmental mastery, indicating individuals are likely to experience an enhanced sense of overall well-being because of their ability to navigate life situations and take advantage of opportunities. Thus, exercising environmental mastery in the context of online dating platforms is necessary for users who seek to improve the quality of their digital dating experience when seeking potential partners.

In Table 4.3 below, the grand total mean score of 3.92 was obtained in the domain of personal growth, falling in the ‘Above Average’, this implies that users of online dating apps are receptive to new experiences and view themselves as individuals with evolving potential, particularly in self-development (Matud et al., 2019). The overall mean score Environmental Mastery Indicators Mean Verbal Interpretation 2. In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live. 4.09 Above Average 8. The daily demands often make me feel discouraged. 3.52 Above Average 14. I do not feel like I fit in with the people and community around me. 3.47 Average 20. I am quite able to manage my daily responsibilities. 4.24 Above Average 26. I often feel overburdened by my responsibilities 3.93 Above Average 32. I have trouble managing my life in a way 3.64 Above Average 38. I have been able to build my house and live according to what I like. 3.58 Above Average Grand Total Mean: 3.78 Above Average 59 Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High implies a moderately positive inclination towards personal growth, which contributes to a significant level of psychological well-being.

Table 4.3. *Personal Growth Domain*

Personal Growth		
Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3. I am not interested in activities that will broaden my perspective.	2.91	Average
9. I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge the way I think about myself and the world.	4.82	High
15. When I think about it, I realize that I have not developed into a better human being.	3.52	Above Average
21. I feel that as a person, I have improved a lot over time.	4.47	Above Average
27. I feel uncomfortable in new situations that require me to change the way I work that has become my habit.	3.86	Above Average
33. For me, life is a continuous process of learning, changing, and growing.	5.09	High
39. I no longer try to make major improvements or changes in my life for a long time.	2.79	Average
Grand Total Mean:	3.92	Above Average

Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High

These findings align with Gao and McLellan (2018) study, which found a correlation between psychological well-being and personal growth. This implies that the well-being of individuals is often enhanced when they actively participate in the learning process, embrace change, and take steps toward personal improvement. Thus, in the context of online dating apps, individuals who have this kind of

mindset and attitude could employ it to improve their overall well-being and as an approach to cope when faced with obstacles that these applications may bring. Personal Growth Indicators Mean Verbal Interpretation 3. I am not interested in activities that will broaden my perspective. 2.91 Average 9. I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge the way I think about myself and the world. 4.82 High 15. When I think about it, I realize that I have not developed into a better human being. 3.52 Above Average 21. I feel that as a person, I have improved a lot over time. 4.47 Above Average 27. I feel uncomfortable in new situations that require me to change the way I work that has become my habit. 3.86 Above Average 33. For me, life is a continuous process of learning, changing, and growing. 5.09 High 39. I no longer try to make major improvements or changes in my life for a long time. 2.79 Average Grand Total Mean: 3.92 Above Average 60 Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High

Table 4.4 below presents the domain's positive relation with others with a grand total mean score of 3.90 which falls under the 'Above Average' category. Celestine (2021) defines positive relationships with others as strong empathy, endearment, and familiarity that can handle the concern for the well-being of oneself that can affect others to provide an understanding of the give-and-take of relationship.

Table 4.4. *Positive Relations with Others Domain*

Positive Relations with Others		
Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
4. Most people think of me as a person full of love and affection.	4.01	Above Average
10. Maintaining close relationships is difficult and frustrating for me.	3.34	Average
16. I often feel lonely because I have few friends to share ideas with.	3.30	Average
22. I enjoy private and reciprocal conversations with family members or friends.	4.59	High
28. People describe me as a person who likes to share and is willing to spend time with others.	4.09	Above Average
34. I do not experience many warm and trusting relationships with other people.	3.51	Above Average
40. I know that I can trust my friends, and they know I am trustworthy.	4.47	High
Grand Total Mean:	3.90	Above Average

Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High,

5.50-6: Very High

This suggests that a higher total mean score indicates a positive relationship with others, as depicted in the domain. Mertika et al. (2020) elaborate on how positive relationships contribute to well-being in various aspects. Additionally, the study by LoeraMalvaez et al. (2017, as cited by, Paez-Gallego, 2020) emphasizes the conclusiveness of relationships for an individual's overall well-being. Positive Relations with Others Indicators Mean Verbal Interpretation 4. Most people think of me as a person full of love and affection. 4.01 Above Average 10. Maintaining close relationships is difficult and frustrating for me. 3.34 Average 16. I often feel lonely because I have few friends to share ideas with. 3.30 Average 22. I enjoy private and reciprocal conversations with family members or friends. 4.59 High 28. People describe me as a person who likes to share and is willing to spend time with others. 4.09 Above Average 34. I do not experience many warm and trusting relationships with other people. 3.51 Above Average 40. I know that I can trust my friends, and they know I am trustworthy. 4.47 High Grand Total Mean: 3.90 Above Average 61 Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High On the other hand,

Table 4.5 below presents Purpose in Life, a domain under the Psychological Well-being of Ryff. Purpose in Life is a steady, overarching goal to do something that is both personally meaningful and constructively engages with an element of the world outside of oneself (Barksdale, 2022). With the grand total mean score of 3.67, it implies 'Above Average in interpretation. That result stated that participants slightly agreed to know the purpose in life and how it can affect multiple facets of their lives. In addition, this domain also had the highest mean score among the other domains. Explaining this highest mean score among the other domains revealed a strong well-being including a variety of previous measurements (Celestine, 2021).

Table 4.5. *Positive Relations with Others Domain*

Purpose in Life			
Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	
5. I live my life on a daily and do not think much about the future.	3.06	Above Average	
11. I have direction and purpose in life.	4.62	High	
17. My daily activities often seem trivial and unimportant to me.	3.13	Average	
23. I have no definite idea of what I will achieve in life.	3.68	Above Average	
29. I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	3.37	Average	
35. Some people wander aimlessly in life, but I am not one of them.	3.84	Above Average	
41. I sometimes feel that I have played my role in life.	3.99	Above Average	
Grand Total Mean:	3.67	Above Average	

Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High

The Table 4.6 below illustrates a grand total mean score of 3.91 for self-acceptance, indicating an interpretation of 'Above Average.' Meibach (2022) defines self-acceptance as the recognition of both positive and negative personal traits, emphasizing genuine self-awareness, albeit subjectively. This outcome suggests that individuals demonstrate acceptance of themselves as they truly are.

As the total mean score is interpreted as 'Above Average' it has a particular apposite as self-acceptance is a valuable intervention for inevitable life changes, it also affects the way an individual considers the people that surround them (Wahat et al., 2021). This reveals the far-reaching impact of self-acceptance on both personal resilience and social interactions.

Table 4.6. *Self-acceptance Domain*

Self-acceptance			
Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	
6. When I look at my past experiences, I feel happy about everything that has happened.	3.87	Above Average	
12. In general, I am proud of myself and the life I am living.	4.46	Above Average	
18. My daily activities often seem trivial and unimportant to me.	3.75	Above Average	
24. I have no definite idea of what I will achieve in life.	4.27	Above Average	
30. I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	3.33	Average	
36. Some people wander aimlessly in life, but I am not one of them.	3.86	Above Average	
41. I sometimes feel that I have played my role in life.	3.84	Above Average	
Grand Total Mean:	3.91	Above Average	

Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High

In addition, self-acceptance serves as essential in establishing a real connection, increasing users' confidence, fostering effective interaction, and assisting users in dealing with the complexity of online interactions when it comes to online dating sites. Presenting oneself authentically while embracing one's actual self significantly improves the quality of the online dating experience overall (Wahat et al., 2021).

Table 4.7. *Self-acceptance Domain*

Domains	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Autonomy	3.95	Above Average
Environmental Mastery	3.78	Above Average
Personal Growth	3.92	Above Average
Positive Relations	3.90	Above Average
Purpose in Life	3.67	Above Average
Self-acceptance	3.91	Above Average
Grand Total Mean:	3.85	Above Average

Legend – 1-1.49: Very Low, 1.5-2.49: Low, 2.5-3.49: Average, 3.5-4.49: Above Average, 4.50-5.49: High, 5.50-6: Very High

The total mean score in the Psychological Well-being domain was obtained with 3.85, within the ‘Above Average’ category. This implies that users have a generally favorable level of psychological well-being. This finding is supported by Bell (2020), who highlights the positive effects that online dating has on its users’ psychological well-being. The app’s users were found to establish more solid connections with other users, boosting their self-esteem. This aligns with the study’s results that, on average, online dating app users tend to exhibit good psychological well-being. In contrast, Bonilla-Zorita et al. (2023) discovered that online dating services are associated with a decline in psychological well-being, increased depression, reduced self-esteem, lower levels of user body dissatisfaction, and addiction.

Effect of Self-Esteem and Loneliness on Psychological Well-Being of Online Dating App Users

Table 5. *Regression Analysis on the Effect of Self-Esteem to Psychological Well-Being*

Variables	Standardized β / r	Adjusted r^2	p-value	Conclusion
Self-esteem and Psychological Well-being	.47	.035	.000	Reject H_0

IV: Self-esteem

DV: Psychological Well-being

The analysis revealed that the self-esteem of online dating app users has a moderate positive relationship with their psychological well-being (Standardized $\beta / r = 0.47$). Their self-esteem accounts for 3.5% (Adjusted $r^2 = .035$) of the variance in their psychological well-being. The p-value of 0.00 is less than the .05 level of significance, proving that the effect of self-esteem on the psychological well-being of online dating app users is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

To support the findings, Choudhary and Wani (2023) found that self-esteem significantly affects the psychological well-being of online dating app users. It implies that establishing and enhancing self-esteem can be a key factor in fostering the psychological well-being of online dating app users, potentially leading to more satisfying and fulfilling online dating experiences. This finding supports the claim that the psychological wellbeing of online dating app users is significantly influenced by self-esteem. In contrast, Pereira et al. (2017) revealed that self-esteem does not significantly affect the psychological well-being of online dating app users. This underscores the need for further research to uncover the complex interactions of these variables and provide a comprehensive understanding of their effects on online dating platforms.

Table 6. *Regression Analysis on the Effect of Loneliness to Psychological Well-Being*

Variables	Standardized β / r	Adjusted r^2	p-value	Conclusion
Loneliness and Psychological Well-being	.37	.032	.000	Reject H_0

IV: Loneliness

DV: Psychological Well-being

Regression analysis showed that the loneliness of the respondents has a low positive correlation with their psychological well-being (Standardized $\beta / r = 0.37$). Loneliness accounts for 3.2% (Adjusted $r^2 = .032$) of the variance in psychological wellbeing. The p-value of 0.00, which is less than the .05 level of significance, proved that the effect of loneliness on the psychological well-being of

online dating app users is statistically significant. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

The findings support the study of Ishaq et al. (2018) that online dating app users' loneliness significantly affects their psychological well-being. This result aligns with the study's finding, indicating that higher levels of loneliness are associated with lower psychological well-being among users. In contrast, the study by Cahyadi (2019) reported different results, suggesting that the effect of loneliness on psychological well-being may be influenced by various other factors. This finding indicates that while loneliness may have an impact, it might not be the most significant factor affecting psychological well-being.

Integration of Findings

The data from the qualitative (interview) and quantitative (survey) approaches were analyzed, and the results were combined to determine the main priorities for the development of a program for users and non-users of online dating apps. Tables 7 to 9 present the integration of the themes from qualitative data and data from the survey of self-esteem, loneliness, and psychological well-being in quantitative data. Variables Standardized β / r Adjusted r^2 p-value Conclusion Loneliness and Psychological Well-being .37 .032 .000 Reject H_0 .

The researchers organized the information into a table, which acted like a combined display for both qualitative and quantitative. This Table allows the researchers to integrate data from the interview and survey. The researchers improved the general understanding of the data by employing this visual method to identify new insights beyond what was discovered through the interview and survey.

Table 7. *Integration of Qualitative-Quantitative data for Self-Esteem*

<i>QUALITATIVE (Self-Worth and Appraisal Theme)</i>	<i>QUANTITATIVE (Self-Esteem)</i>	<i>INTEGRATED THEME Key Priority Areas</i>
In the realm of online dating apps, users embark on a journey of self-discovery and self-worth evaluation through app interactions. They evaluate the positive and negative aspects of their self-esteem.	The quantitative analysis, using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, reveals that users tend to express positive self-esteem with a mean score of 2.25 (Average).	The integrated theme suggests that positive self-perceptions are projected by users as a result of online dating interactions. A key priority is to support self-esteem, emotional well-being, and a healthy self-perception to enhance the overall experience within online dating platforms.

This table indicates that users engaging in online dating apps tend to display positive self-esteem based on a quantitative score of 2.25 (Average) obtained from the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale. The qualitative insights further highlight that users evaluate their self-worth and self-discovery through interactions on dating apps. The integrated theme emphasizes the projection of positive self-perceptions by users due to these online interactions.

While the overall result leans towards positive self-esteem, there are specific areas within the quantitative data that reflect lower scores. For instance, particular statements such as "I feel that I am a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others" scoring 1.91 and "I feel that I have a number of good qualities" scoring 1.94 suggest lower levels of self-esteem in these particular aspects among users engaged in online dating apps. These lower scores in certain areas of self-esteem highlight the extent to which individuals might perceive themselves less positively or struggle with feelings of worthiness and recognizing their positive attributes within the online dating context.

Thus, designing a program that focuses on enhancing self-esteem in these specific areas can significantly benefit users engaged in online dating platforms. This program could incorporate interventions aimed at strengthening feelings of worth, encouraging self-recognition of positive qualities, and fostering a healthier self-perception. By addressing these specific areas of concern highlighted in the data, the program can contribute to promoting a more positive and fulfilling experience for individuals navigating the realm of online dating.

On the other hand, the integration finding in Table 8 below indicates that users engaging in online dating apps experience a mild level of loneliness, as shown by a mean score of 2.42 on the UCLA Loneliness Scale. This data aligns with the qualitative results that users actively seek genuine connections within the digital platform but simultaneously navigate mild feelings of loneliness.

Moreover, the findings reveal an overall mild level of loneliness among online dating app users. However, specific aspects such as "How often do you feel part of a group of friends?" scoring 2.03 and "How often do you feel close to people?" scoring 2.13 reflect lower scores, suggesting particular areas where users might experience heightened feelings of loneliness within their social connections. These lower scores pinpoint areas where individuals might struggle to feel part of a group or experience closeness with others, potentially contributing to their sense of loneliness within online dating platforms.

Table 8. *Integration of Qualitative-Quantitative data for loneliness*

QUALITATIVE (Seeking Connection in a Digital World Theme)	QUANTITATIVE (Loneliness)	INTEGRATED THEME Key Priority Areas
Users seek genuine connections in a digital world and experience mild loneliness. They navigate the feelings of digital comfort in response to loneliness and digital frustrations stemming from online dating experiences.	The quantitative data, measured using the UCLA Loneliness Scale, reveals a mean score of 2.42 (Average), indicating a mild level of loneliness among online dating app users.	The integrated theme suggests that users encounter mild loneliness in online dating. A key priority is to enhance digital comfort, manage frustrations, and promote meaningful connections in the online dating world, with the goal of reducing loneliness and dissatisfaction among users.

Thus, addressing the specific aspects of heightened loneliness identified within this study is crucial in developing a program tailored to users within online dating platforms. This program could incorporate strategies aimed at fostering a sense of belonging, encouraging stronger social connections, and creating avenues for users to feel part of a community. Furthermore, establishing a program has the potential to significantly enhance users' experiences by creating a more connected and rewarding digital dating environment.

Lastly, Table 9 below revealed a moderately positive overall psychological well-being among users of online dating apps, signified by a mean score of 3.85 (Above average) across various well-being domains. This suggests that users showcase traits associated with autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. On the other hand, the qualitative insights emphasize that users actively manage their emotional responses triggered by the use of online dating apps, striving for a balanced well-being. The integrated theme underscores users' openness to new experiences and their positive self-perception, both significantly influencing their psychological wellbeing in the realm of online dating.

While the integration findings indicate a moderately positive overall psychological well-being among users of online dating apps, specific areas such as "I no longer try to make major improvements or changes in my life for a long time" scoring 2.79 and "I am not interested in activities that will broaden my perspectives" scoring 2.905 depict lower scores within the quantitative assessment. These lower scores highlight areas where users might struggle to engage in long-term changes or show less interest in activities that stimulate new perspectives. These aspects might impact their overall well-being within the online dating platform, potentially affecting their sense of personal growth and purpose.

Thus, designing a program that addresses these specific areas becomes crucial to enhance users' psychological well-being. This program could incorporate strategies aimed at fostering a proactive approach to life changes and promoting activities that will broaden perspectives within the online dating environment. By focusing on these specific aspects, the program aims to improve users' overall well-being and satisfaction with online dating platforms.

Table 9. *Integration of Qualitative-Quantitative data for Psychological Well-Being*

QUALITATIVE (Seeking Connection in a Digital World Theme)	QUANTITATIVE (Loneliness)	INTEGRATED THEME Key Priority Areas
Users seek genuine connections in a digital world and experience mild loneliness. They navigate the feelings of digital comfort in response to loneliness and digital frustrations stemming from online dating experiences.	The quantitative data, measured using the UCLA Loneliness Scale, reveals a mean score of 2.42 (Average), indicating a mild level of loneliness among online dating app users.	The integrated theme suggests that users encounter mild loneliness in online dating. A key priority is to enhance digital comfort, manage frustrations, and promote meaningful connections in the online dating world, with the goal of reducing loneliness and dissatisfaction among users.

Conclusion

Online dating app users actively seek validation and connections, influencing emotional experiences and self-perception in digital platforms. This emphasizes the significance of these platforms as spaces for self-assessment and connection-building.

Challenges like persistent loneliness significantly affect users' emotional well-being in online dating, highlighting the importance of recognizing psychological effects for a positive experience.

Coping mechanisms, such as setting boundaries and self-care practices, are important tools for users to navigate changing dynamics in online interactions and maintain emotional balance.

The observed moderately positive self-esteem among online dating app users indicates a generally affirmative self-perception within the context of online dating.

Online dating app users experience a moderate level of occasional disconnection balanced with social interaction, falling within the 'Average' range in terms of loneliness within the online dating app environment.

Online dating app users demonstrate predominantly positive psychological well-being across various traits, showcasing resilience and positive attributes within the digital dating landscape.

There's a moderately positive relationship between self-esteem and psychological wellbeing in online dating, underscoring the crucial role of self-esteem in shaping users' overall emotional well-being within this specific context.

Loneliness has a statistically significant but low positive correlation with psychological well-being among online dating app users, acknowledging its influence compared to other factors, such as self-esteem.

The "Swipe Right, Swipe Left: The Realities of Online Dating Apps Program" is designed as a targeted intervention based on these findings, aiming to equip participants with tools to recognize self-worth, enhance communication skills, and nurture positive relationships in the context of online dating platforms.

Based on the conclusions, the study recommends:

Online dating app users have various motives for turning into online dating apps, with the majority seeking validation and connections through meaningful and positive interactions. However, relying on external validations can hinder users' self-perception. Thus, it is recommended to create a program that promotes and enhances users' emotional well-being, fostering self-esteem that comes from within rather than from external sources.

Self-esteem plays a huge role in shaping one's overall well-being, particularly in the context of online dating apps. Thus, school and guidance counselors are encouraged to educate users on recognizing and addressing psychological aspects, offering guidance and support to enhance self-esteem, which can positively influence users' experiences on these platforms.

Having a support system can be crucial when online dating app users deal with the positive and negative aspects of online dating apps, by enabling individuals to freely express themselves about their experiences, families may offer support and lessen feelings of isolation and frustration. Consequently, it is advised to have a supportive environment and engage in a community where they can openly share their experiences.

Psychology students may engage students in practical applications through internships or research projects focused on studying the psychological aspects of online dating apps. They may encourage them to explore coping strategies and interventions to support individuals dealing with emotional distress on online dating platforms.

Users of online dating apps face a variety of challenges, including vulnerability. Thus, mental health practitioners can assist online support groups and counseling sessions that can offer a safe space for online dating app users to express themselves without worrying about criticism.

Online dating app users can take part in workshops or programs that emphasize emotional resilience and self-awareness, and they can learn coping mechanisms as a result. This contains mindfulness exercises to guarantee mental balance. They are also encouraged to look for assistance in communities or groups where they can exchange experiences and gain knowledge from others.

The feeling of loneliness is one of the factors affecting online dating app users to use these kinds of platforms. Future researchers may conduct studies into more focused interventions within these platforms that speak to the needs and concerns of lonely users, which could improve user satisfaction and help lessen the feeling of loneliness.

Professionals in mental health could be helpful in advocating for a strategy that emphasizes users psychological well-being. This means developing social networks, coming up with different strategies outside of using dating apps, and educate individuals about the value of mental health. Thus, mental health professionals might participate in this to assist users of online dating apps.

The "Swipe Right, Swipe Left: The Realities of Online Dating Apps Program" is an intervention that will enhance the psychological well-being and self-esteem of online dating app users while also reduce their feeling of loneliness. The objectives of this program are to help individuals recognize their own value, improve their communication skills, and build healthy relationships on digital platforms.

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